

cultivated were susceptible, scoring 9 on the Standard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale. At the end of Oct, the disease was widespread, with rice in many fields showing coalesced lesions on the leaves

and blighting. Disease incidence was severe in Nov, when round beads of bacterial ooze were observed on badly infected leaves. Disease incidence declined in Dec, probably because of relatively

lower temperatures (27°C-21°C).

There was 323 mm rainfall in Sep and 148.8 mm in Oct, with favorable temperatures and humidity for disease development. □

Pest control and Management INSECTS

Deterrent effects of seed oil and extracts of some meliaceae plants on rice gall midge (GM) oviposition

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We evaluated seed oil of neem *Azadirachata indica*, and seed oil and methanol (M) and petroleum ether (PE) extracts of chinaberry *Melia azedarach* and *M. toosendan* as oviposition deterrents of GM *Orseolia oryzae*, a serious rice pest in China and tropical Asia.

Egg laying decreased in choice and no-choice tests when gravid GM females were caged on rice seedlings sprayed with seed oils or extracts. In the no-choice test, a 2% M-extract of *M. toosendan* and *M. azedarach* reduced egg laying by 96% and 71% (Table 1). In the choice test, a 1% M-extract of *M. toosendan* and *M. azedarach* seed kernel reduced oviposition by 96% and 83%. The PE-extract of chinaberry seed kernels also deterred oviposition. In the no-choice test, a 2% spray application of neem oil or *M. toosendan* oil reduced oviposition by 47% and 85%, but oil application was not as effective in the choice test. However, both M- and PE-extracts sprayed at 1 to 3% concentration significantly reduced the incidence of silvershoots (Table 2). Preliminary inves-

Table 1. Repellent effect of a spray application of 2% emulsified seed oil or extract of chinaberry and neem on GM oviposition, Guangzhou, China, Sep 1983.^a

Treatment (T)	Eggs laid/replication (no.)	Unlaid eggs ^b /female (no.)	Oviposition deterrence ^c (%)
<i>M. toosendan</i> oil	93 b	4 ab	30
<i>M. toosendan</i> PE-extract	52 c	20 a	61
<i>M. toosendan</i> M-extract	6 d	11 ab	96
<i>M. azedarach</i> oil	20 cd	13 ab	85
<i>M. azedarach</i> PE-extract	15 d	10 ab	88
<i>M. azedarach</i> M-extract	39 c	19 a	71
<i>A. indica</i> oil	44 c	2 ab	67
Control (C) (solvent only)	133 a	0 b	0

^aNo-choice test conducted in 6 × 6 cm plastic cups using 12-d-old rice seedlings. Av of 10 replications for each treatment; means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. ^bThe number of unlaid eggs was determined by dissecting GM females shortly after they died. ^cDeterrence (%) = $\frac{C-T}{C} \times 100$; T = eggs laid in the treatment, C = eggs laid in the control.

Table 2. Effect of spray application of 3% emulsified seed oil and extracts of chinaberry and neem on the incidence of silvershoots caused by GM, Guangzhou, China, Oct 1983.^a

Treatment	Seedlings/replication (no.)	Silvershoots/replication (no.)	Silvershoots (%)
<i>M. toosendan</i> oil	75	4	5 b
<i>M. toosendan</i> PE-extract	81	2	2 b
<i>M. toosendan</i> M-extract	76	3	4 b
<i>M. azedarach</i> oil	95	5	5 b
<i>M. azedarach</i> PE-extract	82	3	4 b
<i>M. azedarach</i> M-extract	88	4	4 b
<i>A. indica</i> oil	77	5	6 b
Control (solvent only)	67	18	27 a

^aTrial conducted on 21-d-old rice seedlings grown in a greenhouse. Av of 7 replications for each treatment; means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

tigations showed that neem and chinaberry oils and extracts at 3% concentration had little ovicidal action.

Field trials are underway to evaluate the potential of these plant derivatives in rice insect pest management. □

Integrated control of rice gall midge (GM)

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To follow up earlier experiments, we conducted confirmatory field trials on inte-

grated control of GM *Orseolia oryzae* at the Regional Research Institute, Chiplima, in 1979 and 1980 wet seasons. Susceptible Jaya and resistant Shakti were planted the first week of Jul and fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. Promising chemical control schedules were tested in 100-m² plots. Untreated control plots were also

maintained.

The maximum protection treatment comprising seedling root dip in 0.02% ai isofenphos + 1% urea for 3 h; phorate granules broadcast at 1 kg ai/ha at 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting (DT) followed by quinalphos spray at 0.5 kg ai/ha at 85 DT gave excellent GM control (Table 1).